

TECHNOLOGY OF GROWING EARLY VARIETIES OF APRICOT (ARMENIACA) IN SURKHONDARYO REGION.

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Abstract

This article provides information on the cultivation of early varieties in apricot orchards, agrotechnical works of grafting, fruit storage, tree care technology, and pruning of apricots.

Key words: pritsa, early ripening apricot variety, grafting, storage, cultivation, medicine, healing, tree shaping, pests.

Today, it occupies the 4th place among fruit trees in terms of the area of apricot orchards in mountainous and sub-mountainous areas and irrigated land areas of our Republic. In recent years, intensive reforms have been carried out in our country to ensure food safety, increase the quality of agricultural products and export potential, and this has already started to bear its results in the agricultural sector.

Currently, if the varieties and types of regionalized fruit crops are selected and placed correctly according to the soil and climate conditions of the place, if all agrotechnical works related to soil cultivation and plant care are performed in a timely and quality manner, fruit growing is highly profitable in plant science, becomes a network with high economic indicators.

MAIN PART

Apricot (*Armeniaca*) is a fruit tree belonging to the Rosaceae family, 5-8 m tall, sometimes up to 17 m. The body and branches are covered with brown bark. The leaves are ovate, oblong-ovate, sharp-pointed, saw-edged, arranged in a row on the stem and branches in a long bandiordam. The flowers are white or pink, five-lobed. The fruit is a yellow, golden, reddish-colored, different-sized, large-sized, dry, grainy fruit with a pleasant taste and smell. It is considered a fruit tree belonging to the ranogul family and belongs to the apricot family. There are 8 species in this family, which are mainly distributed in East, Central Asia and the Caucasus. 10 species are known in Asia. There are more than 500 varieties that were cultivated in Central Asia and China 5 thousand years ago, and in Southern Europe 2 thousand years ago. Common apricot (*Armeniaca vulgaris* Lam). It grows in abundance in the mountains of Central Asia in the form of small apricot groves, up to 8-12 meters in height and 30-40 cm in diameter. Lives up to 150 years. Apricot blooms without producing leaves in March-April. The fruit is round, ovoid, up to 4 cm long, yellow, reddish, sweet in taste. The length of the grain is up to 2 cm, the weight of 1000 grains is 1200 grams. Apricots are propagated from seeds, the germination rate is 95%. Its fruit is used as an important raw material in the food industry. The fruit contains vitamins C and V, carotene 5-20%, and sugar. Danak pulp contains

45-58% oil. Besides, apricot is widely used in the mountains, in forest reclamation, and in the strengthening of eroded mountain slopes. Many large-fruited folk selection varieties of apricot are widespread. Fruits are eaten ripe and dried. The total world harvest of apricots is 2.7 million tons.

It is 35 thousand tons in Uzbekistan. Apricot tree is distinguished from the varieties belonging to the European group by its strong and fast growth, early harvest, long life, resistance to heat and drought. For the growth and development of trees and the ripening of apricot fruits, a useful temperature of 25 C is required. Apricot trees differ in their resistance to severe cold.

Pritsa ertapishar o'rik navi Seedlings planted in 2017 (ready for planting within 5 years of stratification) by "Gold Agro Fresh" LLC enterprise located in Khalkabad district, Termiz district, Surkhandarya region, began to harvest from the 2nd year. Pritsia apricot variety was brought from Italy in 2017 and planted in April in 5x4 and 5x2 schemes. At the same time, several other early and mid-ripening Borsolina, Rubitsa, Lagadur varieties were also brought and are being planted by drip irrigation. At the time of irrigation, up to 5 liters of water is given to each datakht.

Pritsia apricot variety differs from ordinary apricots in that it ripens early, its fruit is very beautiful in terms of appearance, it is exportable, and it has a large storage capacity. In the south of Uzbekistan, it ripens and is harvested from April 20. It blooms in February, it is 3-4 meters tall, the leaves are egg-shaped, the flowers are white, the fruits are fleshy and round, the color is dark red, and they are well separated from the seeds. The fruit is located on the trunk of the tree and along the body. It develops well in Surkhandarya temperature, is heat resistant and fruitful.

Picture 1. Flowering and harvest of Pritsia apricot variety.

In the food industry, it is widely used in the preparation of jam, juice, pickles, leaves, compotes, preserves. At the moment, "Gold Agro Fresh" LLC is carrying out intensive reforms in terms of the quality of its products, the preservation and export potential of apricots. preserves and strengthens its strength.

Picture 2. Preparation for export and storage of Pritsia apricot fruit.

Medicine. Apricot kernel oil and tree glue are used in medicine. The pulp of the fruit contains up to 27% sugar, 2.5% organic acids (malic, citric acid), carotene, vitamins C and RR, flavonoids, pectin, minerals, flavoring substances, 30-50% fat in the pulp, emulsin enzyme. Apricots contain up to 8.43% of amygdalin glycoside. and bitter apricot kernels are used to make bitter almond water. Apricot gum, like gum arabic, consists of arabin and dissolves well in water. Dried apricot fruit (pickle) is used in folk medicine, it is rich in potassium and is recommended for cardiovascular diseases. If the pickle is cooled and drunk, it softens the stomach, improves the functioning of the gastrointestinal system, and increases the excretion of urine (bo in kidney stone diseases).

Even if it is drunk in cases of high blood pressure and jaundice, it is also beneficial. Since the apricot fruit contains a lot of potassium, it is good for the heart.

It is useful to consume in deficiency diseases. But taking into account that the fruit contains sugar, it cannot be given to people with diabetes.

Grafting for apricots. Seedlings grown from local clones of apricot (Kashaki apricot) are the best grafts. From this graft, a strong-growing, long-lived tree is formed it is not picky about the soil, it is resistant to drought. Apricot seedlings can be easily identified in nurseries by their dark pink or reddish roots. It keeps well in other cultural varieties of apricot. The local apricot grown in the regions of Khorezm and Karakalpakstan is different in its resistance to salt. Cultivated varieties of apricot for grafting on gray soils: Khurmo, Mirsanjali, Isfarak, and Amudarya on salty soil. Seedlings of local apricots of white graft and red graft are used

Apricot grafting. Seed fruit trees by bud grafting

reproduction is easier and more convenient. Budded grafts can be harvested when the trees are dormant or during the spring growing season. In the process of harvesting, the shape of the shoots should be given importance. Round

flowers usually sprout from the buds, and branches grow from the pointed buds. For apricots, seed seedlings grown from local clones of apricots (Hashaki Orik) are the best grafts. From this graft, a strong-growing, long-lived tree is formed, it is not picky about the soil, it is resistant to drought. Apricot seedlings can be easily recognized in nurseries by their dark pink

or reddish roots. It keeps well in other cultural varieties of apricot. The local apricot grown in the regions of Khorezm and Karakalpakstan differs in its resistance to salt. Cultivated varieties of apricot are used for grafting on gray soils: Khurmoi, Mirsanjali, Isfarak, and seedlings of local apricot cultivars Aq paivandi and Kyzyl paivandi, grown on the banks of the Amudarya, are used for brackish soil. In the south of Surkhandarya, the shoots are grafted mainly in the last decade of August, grafting is carried out 10 times from February 15.

This tree develops well in Surkhandarya temperature, is heat resistant and fruitful

Figure 3. Methods of grafting and shaping apricots

It is carried out in order to give shape to an apricot tree, as well as to remove diseased, old, broken and redundant branches of the tree, to rejuvenate old trees. The impact on bush trees is one of the most active agrotechnical methods, it increases the productivity of trees by three times, increases the size of fruits up to 20%, improves their quality, while the fruit becomes colorful and juicy, rejuvenates trees, and increases the productivity of the garden. prolongs life. When shortening branches, 1/2 or 1/3 of long branches are removed, depending on the strength of growth. During the growing season, pruning of branches is carried out in May-June, depending on the growth strength and biological characteristics (such a branch is called a green branch), as a result, the growth of the branch stops, axillary buds are formed on the branch, and new branches appear. . Trees are mainly bushed in autumn-winter and winter-spring.

Special tools such as pruning shears, garden knife, vine shears, bow saw and garden table are used in the bush.

The main pests and diseases of Pritsa variety; spider mites, aphids, gray spots and all kinds of pests are causing damage. Aphids are affected by aphids from fruiting to ripening. Excessive moisture in the air causes spotting (klestosporiosis). To prevent these, chemical and agrotexile methods are used.

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